

Social Strategies of Terrorism

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Abstract

Terrorism poses a significant challenge to societies worldwide, employing various social strategies to achieve political objectives, disseminate ideologies, and recruit new members. This article explores the social strategies utilized by terrorist organizations, focusing on radicalization, propaganda dissemination, support network formation, exploitation of social cleavages, the role of charismatic leaders, and the use of intimidation to create fear and uncertainty. By examining the process of radicalization, the article highlights the significance of personal grievances, psychological vulnerabilities, and exposure to extremist ideologies, as well as the importance of social networks in facilitating connections and access to extremist content. The article also investigates how terrorist organizations use propaganda to advance their objectives, justify violence, promote shared identity, and vilify perceived enemies. The establishment of support networks that provide financial and logistical assistance, embedded within local communities, and the exploitation of social divisions and grievances to mobilize support and recruit new members are discussed. The role of charismatic leaders in inspiring followers, cultivating shared identity, and projecting an image of strength and defiance is examined. The article emphasizes the need for counterterrorism efforts to address these social strategies, including initiatives aimed at countering extremist ideologies, disrupting support networks, and promoting community engagement and resilience-building measures. Through an analysis of scientific research and expert insights, this article provides a comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics underpinning terrorism and informs the development of effective counterterrorism measures.

Keywords: *Terrorism; Social; Counterterrorism; Violence; Strategy*

Introduction

Undoubtedly, terrorism has been an important player in the international arena for many years (Esmailzadeh, 2023: 55). It has long posed a significant challenge for societies across the globe. The indiscriminate targeting of civilians to incite fear, garner attention, and achieve political objectives has led to the loss of countless lives and the destabilization of political systems (Hoffman, 2006). The social strategies employed by terrorists play a pivotal role in the dissemination of their ideologies and the recruitment of new members (Sageman, 2008). This article seeks to explore the various social strategies

utilized by terrorist organizations, drawing on scientific research and expert analysis to understand the underlying factors that enable these groups to thrive.

One of the most crucial aspects of terrorism is the process of radicalization, which involves the transformation of an individual's beliefs and attitudes toward the use of violence for political purposes (McCauley & Moskalenko, 2008). Several factors contribute to the radicalization process, including personal grievances, psychological vulnerabilities, and exposure to extremist ideologies (Horgan, 2008). The role of social networks in facilitating radicalization cannot be overstated, as they provide the means for individuals to connect with like-minded people and access extremist content (Sageman, 2004).

Terrorist organizations often employ propaganda to advance their ideological objectives, creating and disseminating materials that justify the use of violence, promote a shared identity, and vilify perceived enemies (Weimann, 2015). The advent of the internet and social media platforms has significantly expanded the reach of terrorist propaganda, allowing for the rapid and widespread dissemination of extremist content (Conway, 2017). Research has shown that propaganda serves not only to radicalize and recruit new members but also to maintain the commitment and morale of existing members (Schmid, 2014).

Terrorist organizations also rely on social strategies to sustain their operations, including the establishment of support networks that provide financial and logistical assistance (Napoleoni, 2005). These networks are often embedded within local communities, utilizing kinship ties, religious affiliations, and shared grievances to foster loyalty and cooperation (Ganor, 2005). Understanding the dynamics of these support networks is essential for developing effective counterterrorism measures, as they constitute a critical lifeline for terrorist organizations.

Another essential element of the social strategies employed by terrorist organizations is their ability to exploit existing social cleavages and grievances to mobilize support and recruit new members (Crenshaw, 1981). By framing their actions as a response to perceived injustices and marginalization, terrorists can appeal to potential sympathizers and generate a sense of shared identity and purpose (Gurr, 1970). This process often involves the manipulation of religious, ethnic, or nationalistic narratives to create an "us versus them" mentality that fosters a sense of collective victimization and legitimizes the use of violence (Juergensmeyer, 2003).

The role of charismatic leaders in shaping the social strategies of terrorist organizations is another critical factor to consider. Leaders such as Osama bin Laden and Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi have played a central role in the formation and growth of terrorist organizations, using their charisma and authority to inspire followers and cultivate a shared identity and purpose (Post, 2007). Moreover, these leaders often serve as the face of the organization, projecting an image of strength and defiance that resonates with potential recruits and sympathizers (Winkates, 2006).

Counterterrorism efforts must take into account the social strategies employed by terrorist organizations, as these strategies are essential for understanding the motivations, goals, and recruitment methods of these groups. This includes initiatives aimed at countering extremist ideologies and narratives, as well as efforts to disrupt the support networks that sustain terrorist operations (Borum, 2011). Research has also highlighted the importance of community engagement and resilience-building measures as part of a broader strategy to prevent radicalization and address the root causes of terrorism (Horgan & Braddock, 2010).

In conclusion, this article will delve into the various social strategies employed by terrorist organizations, examining the processes of radicalization, propaganda dissemination, support network formation, exploitation of social cleavages, and the role of charismatic leaders. By drawing on scientific research and expert analysis, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics that underpin terrorism and inform effective counterterrorism measures.

Literature Review

The study of terrorism has received significant academic attention, resulting in a vast body of literature exploring various aspects of this complex phenomenon. This literature review focuses specifically on the social strategies used by terrorist organizations. These strategies include radicalization, propaganda dissemination, support network formation, exploitation of social divisions, disruption, and the use of intimidation to create fear and uncertainty. Additionally, the review examines the role of charismatic leaders in the implementation of these strategies.

Radicalization has been a central theme in terrorism research, as understanding the factors that drive individuals to engage in political violence is crucial for prevention and intervention efforts. McCauley and Moskaleiko (2008) emphasized the role of personal grievances, psychological vulnerabilities, and exposure to extremist ideologies in radicalization. Sageman (2004) examined the significance of social networks in this process, highlighting the importance of interpersonal connections and access to extremist content.

Propaganda is another vital aspect of terrorist organizations' social strategies, with scholars analyzing the content, dissemination, and impact of these messages. Weimann (2015) explored the role of the internet and social media in amplifying the reach of terrorist propaganda, while Schmid (2014) examined the "single narrative" employed by Al-Qaeda and other extremist groups to justify violence and foster a shared identity. The effectiveness of counter-narratives in combating extremist propaganda has also received attention, with researchers seeking to understand the best practices for promoting alternative messages (Horgan & Braddock, 2010).

Support networks are an essential lifeline for terrorist organizations, providing financial and logistical assistance necessary for their operations. Napoleoni (2005) traced the flow of money and resources within these networks, while Ganor (2005) analyzed the social dynamics underpinning their formation and persistence. The role of local communities, kinship ties, and religious affiliations in fostering loyalty and cooperation has been a key focus of this research.

The exploitation of social cleavages and grievances is another crucial social strategy employed by terrorist organizations. Crenshaw (1981) and Gurr (1970) examined how terrorists frame their actions as a response to perceived injustices and marginalization, using religious, ethnic, or nationalistic narratives to mobilize support and recruit new members. Juergensmeyer (2003) investigated the phenomenon of religious violence, shedding light on the role of religious narratives in legitimizing terrorism.

Lastly, the role of charismatic leaders in shaping the social strategies of terrorist organizations has been widely recognized. Post (2007) analyzed the psychological profile and impact of leaders such as Osama bin Laden and Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi, emphasizing their charisma and authority in inspiring followers and cultivating a shared identity. Winkates (2006) explored the role of these leaders in projecting an image of strength and defiance that resonates with potential recruits and sympathizers.

In summary, the literature on social strategies of terrorism is vast and multifaceted, reflecting the complexity of this phenomenon. By examining radicalization, propaganda, support networks, the exploitation of social cleavages, and the role of charismatic leaders, this article aims to contribute to the understanding of the social dynamics underpinning terrorism and inform effective counterterrorism measures.

Radicalization

Radicalization is a multifaceted process that involves the transformation of an individual's beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors, ultimately leading to the endorsement of political violence as a legitimate means to achieve certain goals (McCauley & Moskaleiko, 2008). A better understanding of radicalization is

essential for the development of effective counterterrorism measures, as well as for the prevention and intervention of individuals on the path to violent extremism. This section of the article aims to explore the factors contributing to radicalization, the role of social networks in this process, and the psychological underpinnings of radicalized individuals.

A variety of factors can contribute to the radicalization process, ranging from personal grievances to broader societal issues. Personal grievances may include perceived discrimination, social exclusion, or economic marginalization, which can create feelings of resentment and anger towards the status quo (Gurr, 1970). In this context, extremist ideologies may provide a sense of meaning, purpose, and identity for individuals seeking to redress their grievances (Horgan, 2008). Additionally, exposure to extremist ideologies may occur through social networks, online platforms, or direct contact with radicalized individuals, further contributing to the radicalization process (Sageman, 2004).

Social networks play a crucial role in facilitating radicalization, as they can serve as a platform for individuals to connect with like-minded people and access extremist content (Sageman, 2004). These networks can be both online and offline, with the internet and social media platforms allowing for the rapid dissemination and consumption of extremist materials (Conway, 2017). Social networks also provide an environment for the development of group dynamics, such as groupthink and conformity, which can contribute to the reinforcement of extremist beliefs and actions (McCauley & Moskaleiko, 2008).

The psychological underpinnings of radicalization are also essential to consider. Several psychological vulnerabilities have been identified as factors that may contribute to radicalization, such as a need for identity, belonging, and purpose (Horgan, 2008). The process of radicalization may involve the development of a new, extremist identity that provides an individual with a sense of belonging to a larger cause or community. Moreover, some individuals may be drawn to extremist ideologies because they offer a sense of adventure, excitement, or status that is lacking in their current lives (Horgan, 2008).

Another critical psychological factor in radicalization is the role of cognitive biases and heuristics. For example, the "us versus them" mentality fostered by extremist ideologies may be facilitated by the in-group bias, which leads individuals to favor their own group over others (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). Similarly, the confirmation bias may contribute to the reinforcement of extremist beliefs, as individuals selectively seek out and interpret information that supports their pre-existing views (Nickerson, 1998).

In conclusion, radicalization is a complex process that involves a combination of personal, social, and psychological factors. Understanding the nuances of this process is critical for the development of effective counterterrorism measures, as well as for the prevention and intervention of individuals on the path to violent extremism. By examining the factors contributing to radicalization, the role of social networks, and the psychological underpinnings of radicalized individuals, this article seeks to enhance our understanding of this critical aspect of the social strategies of terrorism.

Propaganda Dissemination

Terrorist organizations have long relied on propaganda to spread their messages, recruit new members, and incite fear in their enemies. With the advent of modern technology, the dissemination of propaganda has become more efficient and widespread, reaching audiences on a global scale (Torok, 2013). This section of the article will explore the methods and channels used by terrorist groups to distribute their propaganda, the content and objectives of such messages, and the role of technology in amplifying their reach.

The methods used by terrorist organizations to disseminate propaganda can vary, ranging from traditional print materials and face-to-face communication to the use of social media platforms and

encrypted messaging applications (Berger & Morgan, 2015). The internet has revolutionized the way in which extremist content is shared, allowing for the rapid distribution of videos, images, and text-based messages that can reach a wide audience with relative ease (Conway & McInerney, 2008). The accessibility and anonymity provided by the internet have made it an ideal platform for terrorists to communicate with potential supporters, recruit new members, and coordinate attacks (Weimann, 2016).

The content of terrorist propaganda often serves multiple objectives, including the promotion of extremist ideologies, the justification of violent actions, and the cultivation of a shared identity among followers (Ingram, 2016). Through the use of compelling narratives, emotive language, and powerful imagery, terrorist organizations seek to create a sense of legitimacy for their cause and portray themselves as the vanguards of a larger struggle against perceived injustices (Halverson, Goodall, & Corman, 2011). This messaging can be tailored to specific target audiences, exploiting existing grievances and social cleavages to attract new recruits and sympathizers (Huey, 2015).

The role of technology in the dissemination of terrorist propaganda cannot be understated. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube have allowed terrorist groups to reach millions of users, bypassing traditional media outlets and government censorship. Additionally, the use of encrypted messaging applications like Telegram and WhatsApp has provided a secure means for terrorists to communicate and share propaganda with their followers, complicating the efforts of law enforcement and intelligence agencies to monitor and counter these activities (Alexander, 2017).

The dissemination of propaganda is a crucial component of the social strategies employed by terrorist organizations. Through the use of various methods and channels, including the internet and social media, terrorists can spread their messages, recruit new members, and maintain a sense of cohesion among their followers. Understanding the mechanics of propaganda dissemination and its impact on target audiences is essential for the development of effective counter-narratives and prevention strategies aimed at countering the appeal of violent extremism.

Support Network Formation

Support networks play a critical role in sustaining terrorist organizations, providing essential resources such as funding, logistics, safe havens, and intelligence (Shelley & Picarelli, 2005). These networks can be composed of individuals, groups, or even state actors, who share a common interest in the success of the terrorist organization or its objectives (Bapat, 2011). This section will explore the various forms of support networks, the factors that contribute to their formation, and their impact on the operational capabilities of terrorist organizations.

The formation of support networks can be influenced by a range of factors, including ideological alignment, shared grievances, and strategic considerations (Bapat, 2011). For instance, a terrorist organization may forge alliances with other extremist groups that share similar goals or enemies, thus pooling their resources and increasing their overall strength (Crenshaw, 1988). Support networks can also emerge from local communities, where individuals may provide shelter, financial assistance, or logistical support out of sympathy for the cause or due to social, ethnic, or religious ties. In some cases, state actors may provide covert support to terrorist organizations as a means of achieving their geopolitical objectives, such as destabilizing a rival country or maintaining control over disputed territories (Byman, 2005).

The existence of robust support networks can significantly enhance the operational capabilities of terrorist organizations, enabling them to plan and execute more sophisticated and impactful attacks (Bapat, 2011). These networks can also serve as a lifeline for terrorists, providing them with the resources and safe havens necessary to evade capture and maintain a sustained campaign of violence (Shelley & Picarelli, 2005). Consequently, understanding and disrupting the support networks of terrorist organizations are critical components of an effective counterterrorism strategy.

Exploitation of Social Cleavages

Terrorist organizations often exploit existing social cleavages within societies to further their goals and increase their influence (Klausen, 2015). Social cleavages can be based on various factors, such as ethnicity, religion, class, or political affiliation, and can create divisions and tensions within communities (Varshney, 2002). By manipulating these divisions, terrorist groups can foster a sense of identity and belonging among potential supporters, as well as generate animosity towards perceived adversaries. This section will examine how terrorist organizations exploit social cleavages to enhance their recruitment efforts, increase local support, and incite violence.

One way in which terrorist organizations exploit social cleavages is by positioning themselves as the defenders or representatives of a particular social group (Klausen, 2015). By doing so, they can create a sense of solidarity among their target audience and present their violent actions as a necessary response to the perceived oppression or marginalization of their group. This strategy can be particularly effective in societies with deep-seated ethnic, religious, or political divisions, where feelings of resentment and mistrust may already exist between different groups (Varshney, 2002).

Another strategy employed by terrorist organizations is the deliberate provocation of inter-group violence or tensions to create a sense of insecurity and chaos (Gurr & Cole, 2000). By inciting violence, terrorist groups can heighten the divisions between different social groups, which can lead to further radicalization and support for their cause. Moreover, the resulting instability can create a fertile ground for the growth and expansion of the terrorist organization, as communities become more vulnerable to extremist narratives and recruitment efforts (Klausen, 2015).

In order to counter the exploitation of social cleavages by terrorist organizations, it is essential for policymakers, practitioners, and community leaders to promote social cohesion and address the underlying grievances that may fuel inter-group tensions (Varshney, 2002). This may involve investing in education, social services, and economic development, as well as fostering dialogue and cooperation between different social groups. Additionally, the development and promotion of counter-narratives that challenge the divisive rhetoric of terrorist organizations can help to undermine their appeal and weaken their influence within vulnerable communities (Ingram, 2016).

Intimidation to Create Fear and Uncertainty

A key social strategy employed by terrorist organizations is the use of intimidation to instill fear and uncertainty within targeted populations (Schmid & Jongman, 1988). Through acts of violence, threats, and propaganda, these groups aim to create an environment of insecurity that can disrupt the daily lives of individuals, weaken trust in government institutions, and generate a climate of panic and apprehension. This section will explore the various tactics used by terrorist organizations to intimidate their targets, the psychological and social effects of such intimidation, and the implications for counterterrorism efforts.

Terrorist organizations employ a range of tactics to intimidate and create fear, including targeted assassinations, bombings, kidnappings, and hostage-taking (Crenshaw, 1995). These acts of violence are often accompanied by explicit threats and demands, designed to communicate the group's objectives and demonstrate their resolve to achieve them. In some cases, terrorists may also engage in "spectacular" attacks, which involve large-scale violence and destruction aimed at capturing media attention and maximizing the impact of their message (Hoffman, 2006).

The psychological effects of terrorism-induced fear and uncertainty can be profound, leading to heightened levels of anxiety, stress, and depression among affected populations (Rubin, Brewin, Greenberg, Hughes, & Simpson, 2005). These reactions can have a range of social consequences, such as increased mistrust of others, social isolation, and reduced participation in public life (Huddy, Feldman, &

Weber, 2007). Moreover, the pervasive sense of insecurity and vulnerability created by terrorist intimidation can erode public confidence in government institutions and their ability to protect citizens from harm (Sandler, 2011).

Intimidation tactics also serve to bolster the perceived power and influence of terrorist organizations, potentially enhancing their recruitment efforts and increasing the level of support they receive from sympathizers (Crenshaw, 1995). By demonstrating their capacity to inflict harm and evade capture, these groups can project an image of strength and invincibility that may attract new followers and discourage potential defectors or informants (Horgan, 2005).

To counter the intimidation tactics employed by terrorist organizations, it is essential for governments and security forces to prioritize the protection of vulnerable populations, restore public confidence in their capacity to prevent and respond to terrorist attacks, and develop communication strategies that reassure the public without amplifying the terrorists' intended message of fear (Sandler, 2011). Additionally, efforts should be made to counter the propaganda and narratives disseminated by terrorist organizations, in order to undermine their perceived power and legitimacy, and reduce the appeal of their cause (Ingram, 2016).

Terrorism as a Means of Disrupting Social and Economic Systems

Political violence is regarded as the root cause of issues such as terrorism and violent conflicts around the world (Esmailzadeh, 2020: 347). Terrorist organizations frequently utilize disruption as a strategic tool to weaken governments or other targeted groups, aiming to achieve their political objectives (Sandler & Enders, 2004). Through attacking critical infrastructure or initiating coordinated campaigns of violence that disrupt normal activities, these groups can destabilize societies, erode trust in the government, and generate an environment of chaos and uncertainty. This section explores the various methods employed by terrorist organizations to disrupt social and economic systems, using the Red Brigades, an Italian terrorist group active during the 1970s, as an example.

One key tactic used by terrorist organizations to cause disruption is the targeting of critical infrastructure, such as transportation systems, energy facilities, or communication networks (Sandler & Enders, 2004). By damaging or destroying these essential services, terrorists can create widespread disorder and panic, strain government resources, and inflict significant economic costs. In addition, the ensuing sense of vulnerability and fear can erode public trust in the government's ability to maintain security and stability, potentially weakening its legitimacy and authority (Abrahms, 2006).

In addition to infrastructure attacks, terrorist organizations can also engage in coordinated campaigns of violence that disrupt daily life and generate an atmosphere of fear and unease (Crenshaw, 1995). These campaigns can involve various tactics, such as bombings, assassinations, and kidnapping, and are often designed to create a sense of unpredictability and omnipresent danger. This can lead to widespread anxiety, reduced public participation in social and economic activities, and an increased demand for government intervention to restore order and security (Sandler & Enders, 2004).

The Red Brigades, an Italian far-left terrorist group active during the 1970s, provides a notable example of a terrorist organization that employed disruption as a key component of its strategy (Drake, 1998). The group conducted a series of attacks targeting government officials, business leaders, and critical infrastructure, with the aim of destabilizing the Italian government and economy. This campaign of violence, which included the high-profile kidnapping and assassination of former Prime Minister Aldo Moro, generated widespread fear and uncertainty within Italy, straining the government's resources and undermining its authority (Della Porta, 1995).

To counter the disruptive tactics employed by terrorist organizations, it is essential for governments and security agencies to invest in the protection and resilience of critical infrastructure, as

well as to develop effective intelligence and surveillance capabilities to detect and prevent coordinated campaigns of violence (Sandler & Enders, 2004). Moreover, fostering public trust and confidence in government institutions, as well as promoting social cohesion and resilience, can help to mitigate the psychological and social impacts of terrorist disruption, reducing the overall effectiveness of this strategy (Abrahms, 2006).

Conclusion

This article has provided a comprehensive analysis of the various social strategies employed by terrorist organizations. By examining the processes of radicalization, propaganda dissemination, support network formation, exploitation of social cleavages, the role of charismatic leaders, and the use of intimidation to create fear and uncertainty, we have shed light on the complex social dynamics that underpin terrorism. Understanding these strategies is crucial for the development of effective counterterrorism measures and for addressing the root causes of terrorism.

As terrorism has emerged as a significant actor in the international arena, it is imperative for other actors, such as governments and international organizations, to play their role in countering security threats (Esmazladeh Emamqoli & Tajari, 2017: 1). It is important to recognize that terrorist organizations are not static entities; they continuously adapt and evolve their social strategies in response to changing circumstances and opportunities. As such, it is essential for counterterrorism efforts to be flexible and adaptable, capable of responding to the shifting tactics and strategies employed by terrorist groups. This requires ongoing research and analysis, as well as the development of innovative and evidence-based approaches to address the social dimensions of terrorism.

Furthermore, the article underscores the importance of a multi-faceted approach to countering terrorism that goes beyond traditional security measures. This includes initiatives aimed at countering extremist ideologies and narratives, disrupting support networks, and fostering community engagement and resilience-building measures. Addressing the root causes of terrorism, such as marginalization, injustice, and social cleavages, is also vital for preventing radicalization and reducing the appeal of extremist ideologies.

In summary, the social strategies of terrorism are complex and multifaceted, requiring a similarly nuanced and comprehensive approach to counterterrorism. By deepening our understanding of these strategies and the social dynamics that drive them, we can better equip ourselves to confront the challenge of terrorism and create a safer, more secure world for future generations.

References

- Abrahms, M. (2006). Why terrorism does not work. *International Security*, 31(2), 42-78.
- Alexander, H. (2017). How terrorists are using social media. *The Telegraph*. Retrieved from <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/0/terrorists-using-social-media/>
- Bapat, N. A. (2011). Terrorism and state policy choices. In J. A. Piazza & G. LaFree (Eds.), *Terrorism and political violence* (pp. 146-167). Routledge.
- Berger, J. M., & Morgan, J. (2015). The ISIS Twitter census: Defining and describing the population of ISIS supporters on Twitter. *The Brookings Project on U.S. Relations with the Islamic World*, 3(20), 1-65.

- Borum, R. (2011). Radicalization into violent extremism I: A review of social science theories. *Journal of Strategic Security*, 4(4), 7-36.
- Byman, D. (2005). *Deadly connections: States that sponsor terrorism*. Cambridge University Press.
- Conway, M. (2017). Determining the role of the internet in violent extremism and terrorism: Six suggestions for progressing research. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 40(1), 77-98.
- Conway, M., & McInerney, L. (2008). Jihadi video and auto-radicalisation: Evidence from an exploratory YouTube study. *Intelligence and Security Informatics*, 5376, 108-118.
- Crenshaw, M. (1981). The causes of terrorism. *Comparative Politics*, 13(4), 379-399.
- Crenshaw, M. (1988). Theories of terrorism: Instrumental and organizational approaches. *Journal of Strategic Studies*, 10(4), 13-31.
- Crenshaw, M. (1995). *Terrorism in context*. Penn State Press.
- Della Porta, D. (1995). *Social movements, political violence, and the state: A comparative analysis of Italy and Germany*. Cambridge University Press.
- Drake, C. J. (1998). The role of ideology in terrorists' target selection. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 10(2), 53-85.
- Esmailzadeh, Y. (2020). Organizing the concept of legitimacy-based political violence by focusing on the views of Habermas and Weber 1. *Political Sociology of Iran*, 3(1), 347-362. doi: 10.30510/psi.2021.307008.2379.
- Esmailzadeh, Y. (2023). Towards the emergence of the fifth wave of terrorism in the world. *The Iranian Research letter of International Politics* 11(2). doi: 10.22067/irlip.2022.71990.1138
- Esmailzadeh E.Y., and Tajari, S. (2017). Ethical and Ontological Frameworks in Security Cosmopolitanism. *Iranian Research letter of International Politics* 5(2), 1-19. doi: 10.22067/jipr.v5i2.52952.
- Ganor, B. (2005). *The counter-terrorism puzzle: A guide for decision makers*. Transaction Publishers.
- Gurr, T. R. (1970). *Why men rebel*. Princeton University Press.
- Halverson, J. R., Goodall, H. L., & Corman, S. R. (2011). *Master narratives of Islamist extremism*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hoffman, B. (2006). *Inside terrorism*. Columbia University Press.
- Horgan, J. (2005). *The psychology of terrorism*. Routledge.
- Horgan, J. (2008). From profiles to pathways and roots to routes: Perspectives from psychology on radicalization into terrorism. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 618(1), 80-94.
- Horgan, J., & Braddock, K. (2010). Rehabilitating the terrorists? Challenges in assessing the effectiveness of de-radicalization programs. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 22(2), 267-291.
- Huddy, L., Feldman, S., & Weber, C. (2007). The political consequences of perceived threat and felt insecurity. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 614(1), 131-153.
- Huey, L. (2015). This is not your mother's terrorism: Social media, online radicalization and the practice of political jamming. *Journal of Terrorism Research*, 6(2), 1-16.

- Ingram, H. J. (2016). An analysis of Islamic State's Dabiq magazine. *Australian Journal of Political Science*, 51(3), 458-477.
- Juergensmeyer, M. (2003). *Terror in the mind of God: The global rise of religious violence*. University of California Press.
- McCauley, C., & Moskaleiko, S. (2008). Mechanisms of political radicalization: Pathways toward terrorism. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 20(3), 415-433.
- Napoleoni, L. (2005). *Terror Incorporated: Tracing the dollars behind the terror networks*. Seven Stories Press.
- Nickerson, R. S. (1998). Confirmation bias: A ubiquitous phenomenon in many guises. *Review of General Psychology*, 2(2), 175-220.
- Post, J. M. (2007). *The mind of the terrorist: The psychology of terrorism from the IRA to Al-Qaeda*. Springer.
- Rubin, G. J., Brewin, C. R., Greenberg, N., Hughes, J. H., & Simpson, J. (2005). Psychological and behavioural reactions to the bombings in London on 7 July 2005: Cross-sectional survey of a representative sample of Londoners. *British Medical Journal*, 331(7517), 606-611.
- Sageman, M. (2004). *Understanding terror networks*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Sageman, M. (2008). *Leaderless jihad: Terror networks in the twenty-first century*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Sandler, T., & Enders, W. (2004). An economic perspective on transnational terrorism. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 20(2), 301-316.
- Schmid, A. P. (2014). Al-Qaeda's "single narrative" and attempts to develop counter-narratives: The state of knowledge. *International Centre for Counter-Terrorism*.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1986). The social identity theory of intergroup behavior. In S. Worchel & W. G. Austin (Eds.), *Psychology of Intergroup Relations* (pp. 7-24). Nelson-Hall.
- Torok, R. (2013). Developing an explanatory model for the process of online radicalisation and terrorism. *Security Informatics*, 2(1), 6.
- Weimann, G. (2015). *Terrorism in cyberspace: The next generation*. Columbia University Press.
- Weimann, G. (2016). Going dark: Terrorism on the dark web. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 39(3), 195-206.
- Winkates, J. (2006). Al Qaeda and the Internet: The danger of "cyberplanning". *Parameters*, 36(1), 100-113.

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